

THE PRODUCTIVITY OF DERIVATIONAL PATTERNS IN VOCABULARY ENTRIES

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Abstract: *The notions of productivity and non-productivity of derivational patterns, such as prefixes and suffixes were problematic in linguistics for ages, as vocabulary entries becoming larger year by year. In this article, examples of productive and non-productive affixes are given with justification and usages.*

Keywords: *derivational morphology, derivational patterns, productivity, non-productivity, dead affix, living affix, word formation, prefix, suffix, diachronic approach.*

"Derivational morphology studies the principles governing the construction of new words, without reference to the specific grammatical role a word might play in a sentence. In the formation of drinkable from drink, or disinfect from infect, for example, we see the formation of new words, each with its own grammatical properties."¹

Many words in English are formed from the same root or base word. By adding different suffixes, a range of new words can be formed. When a suffix is added to a base word and that base word becomes a noun, it is called a noun suffix. Productivity of derivational affixes should not be identified with their frequency of occurrence in speech, although there may be some interrelation between them. Frequency of occurrence is characterized by the fact that a great number of words containing a derivational affix one often used in speech, in particular in various texts.

Productivity is characterized by the ability of a given suffix to make new words. In the course of its historical development the English language has adopted a great many suffixes and prefixes from foreign languages. The process does not consist in the following derivational affixes as much. It is words that a language borrows from a foreign language and the borrowed words bring with their derivatives formed after the word building patterns of the foreign language. When such pairs as **derive** and **derivation** had found their ways into the English vocabulary it was natural that the suffix **-ation**

¹ David Crystal, "How Language Works." Overlook Press, 2005

should be recognized by English speakers as an allowable means of forming nouns of action out of verbs.

So in conclusion, we can say that a notion that could not possibly have existed at some previous stage has a name formed with the help of some affix, the affix is considered productive. That is to say the word forming activity of the affixes may change in the course of time: some affixes remain productive while others become non-productive.

Distinction is usually made between dead and living affixes². Dead affixes are described as those which are no longer felt in Modern English as component parts of words; they have so fused with the base of the word as to lose their independence completely. It is only by special etymological analysis that they may be singled out, e.g. **-d** in **dead, seed, -le, -l, -el** in **bundle, sail, hovel; -ock** in **hillock; -lock** in **wedlock; -t** in **flight, gift, height**. It is quite clear that dead suffixes are irrelevant to present-day English word-formation, they belong in its diachronic study.

Living affixes may be easily singled out from a word, e.g. the noun-forming suffixes **-ness, -dom, -hood, -age, -ance**, as in **darkness, freedom, childhood, marriage, assistance**, etc. or the adjective-forming suffixes **-en, -ous, -ive, -ful, -y** as in **wooden, poisonous, active, hopeful, Stony**, etc.

However, not all living derivational affixes of Modern English possess the ability to coin new words. Some of them may be employed to coin new words on the spur of the moment, others cannot, so that they are different from the point of view of their productivity. Accordingly, they fall into two basic classes — productive and non-productive word-building affixes.

It has been pointed out that linguists disagree as to what is meant by the productivity of derivational affixes.

Following the first approach all living affixes should be considered productive in varying degrees from highly-productive (e.g. **-er, -ish, -less, re-**, etc.) to non-productive (e.g. **-ard, -cy, -ive**, etc.).

Consequently, it becomes important to describe the constraints imposed on and the factors favouring the productivity of affixational patterns and individual affixes. The degree of productivity of affixational patterns very much depends on the structural, lexico-grammatical and semantic nature of bases and the meaning of the affix. For instance, the analysis of the bases from which the suffix **-ise (-ize)** can derive verbs reveals that it is most productive with noun-stems, adjective-stems also favour its productivity, whereas verb-stems and adverb-stems do not, e.g. **criticise**

²Ginzburg R.S. "A Course in Modern English Lexicology" M., 1979 pp. 125-126

(cf. **critic**), **organise** (cf. **organ**), **itemise** (cf. **item**), **mobilise** (cf. **mobile**), **localise** (cf. **local**), etc.

Comparison of the semantic structure of a verb in **-ise (-ize)** with that of the base it is built on shows that the number of meanings of the stem usually exceeds that of the verb and that its basic meaning favours **the** productivity of the suffix **-ise (-ize)** to a greater degree than its marginal meanings, cf. **to characterise — character, to moralise — moral, to dramatise — drama**, etc.

The treatment of certain affixes as non-productive naturally also depends on the concept of productivity. The current definition of non-productive derivational affixes as those which cannot be used in Modern English for the coining of new words is rather vague and may be interpreted in different ways. Following the definition the term non-productive refers only to the affixes unlikely to be used for the formation of new words, e.g. **-ous, -th, fore-** and some others (cf. **famous, depth, to foresee**).

If one accepts the other concept of productivity mentioned above, then non-productive affixes must be defined as those that cannot be used for the formation of occasional words and, consequently, such affixes as **-dom, -ship, -ful, -en, -ify, -ate** and many others are to be regarded as non-productive.

The degree of productivity of a suffix or, to be more exact, of a derivational affix in general may be established on a statistical basis as the ratio of the number of newly-formed words with the given suffix to the number of words with the same suffix already operating in the language. To give an illustration, we shall take the suffix **-ise (-ize)**. The dictionaries of new words compiled by P. Berg and M. Reifer as well as the Addenda section of Webster's New International Dictionary³ contain 40 new verbs built up with the help of the suffix **-ise (-ize)**. On the other hand, The Thorndike Century Junior Dictionary⁴ has 127 verbs derived by means of the same suffix. A similar examination of the verb-suffixes **-ate, -en, -ify** yields the following results characterising the productivity measure of each of the verbs: the suffix **-ate** - 0.034, the suffix **-en** - 0.018 and the suffix **-ify** - 0.017. Thus, these figures lead one to the conclusion that the suffix **-ise (-ize)** is the most productive of the four under investigation and that the suffix **-ate** is more productive than **-en** and **-ify**.

³ Webster's New International Dictionary - September 1961

⁴ The Thorndike Century Junior Dictionary - by [E. L. Thorndike](#), January 1, 1942

The theory of relative productivity of derivational affixes is also corroborated by some other observations made on English word-formation. For instance, different productive affixes are found in different periods of the history of the language. It is extremely significant, for example, that out of the seven verb-forming suffixes of the Old English period only one has survived up to the present time with a very low degree of productivity, namely the suffix **-en (to soften, to darken, to whiten)**.

A derivational affix may become productive in just one meaning because that meaning is specially needed by the community at a particular phase in its history. This may be well illustrated by the prefix **de-** in the sense of 'undo what has been done, reverse an action or process', E.g., **deacidify** (paint spray), **decentralise** (government or management), **deration** (eggs and butter), **de-reserve** (medical students), **desegregate** (coloured, children), and so on.

Furthermore, there are cases when a derivational affix being non-productive in the non-specialised section of the vocabulary is used to coin scientific or technical terms. This is the case, for instance, with the suffix **-ance** which has been used to form some terms in Electrical Engineering, e.g. **capacitance, impedance, reactance**. The same is true of the suffix **-ity** which has been used to form terms in physics and chemistry such as **alkalinity, luminosity, emissivity** and some others. We can say that productive affixes which are used to form new words on the concept of productivity.

When words contain two or more affixes, they are also referred to as complex words, as opposed to simple words that cannot be analyzed into meaningful parts. Such morphologically complex words are composed of a morpheme root and one or more affixes. Some examples of English roots are act in deactivation, system in unsystematically, ceive in perceive, and cred in incredible. For practical purposes, linguists sometimes use the word base to mean any root or stem to which an affix is attached. Among the elements that can be stripped from deactivation are act, active, activate, and deactivate, which are all bases. In brief, we can say that a root may or may not stand alone as a word⁵.

⁵ Fromkin et al. 2011, p. 47

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